

Research Article

A new combination in *Caulokaempferia* (Zingiberaceae) of Myanmar

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Article Details: Received: 2025-05-10 | Accepted: 2025-06-14 | Available online: 2025-06-16

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Abstract: A new combination is proposed here for *Monolophus unifolius* Y.H.Tan & H.B.Ding under the genus *Caulokaempferia* K.Larsen as *C. unifolia* (Y.H.Tan & H.B.Ding) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar.

Keywords: Endemic, *Monolophus unifolius*, Myanmar

Introduction

The genus *Caulokaempferia* K.Larsen (1964) currently comprises 36 species, distributed from the Eastern Himalayas and Indo-China to Southeast China (POWO, 2025; Singh, 2025). In Myanmar, the genus is represented by five species, namely *C. kayinensis* Picheans. & Sangnark, *C. monensis* Picheans. & Sangnark, *C. odontochila* (Y.H.Tan & H.B.Ding) R.Kr.Singh, *C. secunda* (Wall.) K.Larsen and *C. unifolia* (Y.H.Tan & H.B.Ding) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, of which *C. kayinensis*, *C. monensis*, *C. odontochila* and *C. unifolia* are endemic (POWO, 2025; Singh, 2025). However, the species *Monolophus unifolius* Y.H.Tan & H.B.Ding (2025) requires transfer to the genus *Caulokaempferia*. Accordingly, following the current nomenclatural circumscription of *Caulokaempferia* (Singh, 2025), a new combination is proposed here.

The treatment of *Caulokaempferia* as a superfluous name for *Monolophus* Delafosse, Guill. & Je.Kuhn (1830 a, b) by Mood et al. (2014) is not correct as per ICN (Turland *et al.*, 2018). Based on the current nomenclatural framework, *Monolophus* is considered a synonym of *Kaempferia* L. (Singh, 2025).

New combination

Caulokaempferia unifolia (Y.H.Tan & H.B.Ding) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Monolophus unifolius* Y.H.Tan & H.B.Ding, *Phytotaxa* 698(4): 279. 2025.

Holotype: Myanmar, Sagaing Region, Hkamti District, Hkamti Township, Htamanthi Wildlife Sanctuary, near Nam E Zu Camp 1, 180 m, 25°29'41" N, 95°25'16" E, 1 June 2019, Y.-H. Tan, M. Deng, B. Yang, H.-B. Ding and X.-D. Zeng M5728 (HIBTC).

Distribution: Endemic to northern Myanmar.

Acknowledgments

The lead author is thankful to the Director, Botanical Survey of India, Kolkata and Head of Office, Botanical Survey of India, Arid Zone Regional Centre, Jodhpur for facilities.

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